

Security Capabilities of Combined Cryptography and Video Steganography

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Abstract: *The incidence of unauthorized access to text messages is of great concern despite existing online security systems. Video Steganography and Cryptography are online security systems which prevent unauthorized access to important information. Different researches have been done on these two techniques and having their dual functionalities in one system would make a very strong information security system. With this in mind, a Video Steganography(as a result of its higher embedding capacity) system was set up with an additional security layer of Cryptography. Advanced Encryption Standards (AES) algorithm was used in this study for implementation of the encryption and decryption i.e Cryptography. The Least Significant Bit (LSB) algorithm which was used in this study for embedding the text within the audio of the video file i.e Steganography. The de-multiplexing and multiplexing of the selected video file was achieved with C/C++ programming language while Java programming language was used for the software development.*

Keywords: Cryptography, Steganography, Multilayer Security, Advanced Encryption Standard, Least Significant Bits.

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Introduction

Since the use of computers and the Internet has become a necessity in all works of life [46][47][48][49][50], and information sharing is inevitable in the world we live, shared information comes with a risk of being intercepted by malicious third parties. As a result of this, data and information which pass through media should be properly protected and secured against intruders and unauthorized persons who may use the information against the sender or the intended recipient [37]. As a result, Information Security has evolved into being a very vital part of the world of Information and Communication Technology (ICT)[34]. Over the years, different information hiding techniques have evolved; of which Cryptography and Steganography are some basic types which although, are similar but quite different [20].

Steganography [71][7][9][19] can be defined as the study of invisible communication that usually deals with the ways of hiding the existence of the communicated message. It is a technique used for the hidden exchange of information [20][51]. In this light, if it is successfully achieved, the message does not attract attention from attackers. Using Steganography, information can be hidden in different embedding mediums, known as carriers [4]. Most often times, Steganography and Cryptography are usually mistaken to be the same of which they are quite similar, but very different. Cryptography is an information hiding tool which utilizes mathematical algorithms to convert data into an unreadable form i.e. encryption. It involves converting text into cipher-text such that it is difficult to understand by an attacker [7][9][21].

In Steganography [7][22] data is hidden in a carrier such as Text, Image, Audio or Video such that it is undetectable. While in Cryptography, ordinary text is scrambled into cipher-text [21] such that the altered text can be easily detected by an intruder. Also in Steganography, the intruder is most likely not going to detect any form of hidden information at a glance [1].

While in Cryptography, the structure of the message is scrambled to make it meaningless and

can be reconstructed only by the holder of a key. It offers the ability of transmitting the information between communicating parties in a way that prevents the third party from reading it [3]. Steganography can further be said to be a technique of hiding information in digital media. In contrast to Cryptography, it is not to keep others from knowing the hidden information but it is to keep others from thinking that the information even exists[2]. In order to prevent hackers from tampering with sensitive information, it is of utmost importance to safeguard multimedia content as at when necessary, due to their vulnerability. Though different Steganography methods have evolved over the years, an improvement on an already existing Audio-Video system was proposed of which a multi-layer method was utilized in its implementation.

Conceptual Framework

The implementation of Steganography by K.P. Adhiya and Swati A. Patil [75] was achieved by Hiding Text in Audio Using LSB Based Steganography in Matlab 7 while Mean Opinion Score (MOS) was used to measure the performance of the research. Phase Coding and Spread Spectrum Methods were not used in the implementation of this research. Bhattacharyya Coefficient and Normalized Histogram Intersection Coefficients were not used in measuring the performance of the algorithm. Also Parity Coding, Echo Hiding and Phase Coding were not used in Audio Steganography. Video Steganography was not implemented.

A.K Sen, S. Dutta and S. Dabadgaonkar [76] adopted the Echo Hiding Technique in its implementation of Video Steganography such that a message is embedded in a sound signal by introducing an echo in its discrete signal. Since video files are composed of audio and video files, the audio file of this work was embedded first. To encode the audio file, an echo signal is generated from the original audio signal, of which three of its components: the Amplitude, Decay Rate and Delay Time(Offset) are changed from the original signal. These

components are set below the human hearing threshold, so the echo is not easily detected. While encoding the video file, involves modifying the redundant bits without altering the original image (The Least Significant Bit method). The original audio signal need not be available for detection also the echo signals are imperceptible since it only adds delay. This research did not adopt Phase Coding in its implementation [76].

Steganography by N. Kaur and S. Behal [77] was carried out using the Least Significant Bit (LSB) method in two folds: Firstly, an image cover file is selected as well as the carrier file which could be text or image which would later be converted to binary. After conversion, the carrier file is embedded within the cover file using LSB encryption using edges. Secondly, an audio cover file is converted into binary which embeds an image file into the converted audio file by bitwise embedding. Afterwards, extraction takes place such that the embedded image is taken out of the cover audio file by bitwise extraction, this research adopted more than one approach in its implementation and AES algorithm was utilized in its implementation.

Cryptography

Cryptography was derived from two (2) Greek words "kryptos" and "graphein" meaning hidden writing [58]. Cryptography in ancient times was carried out by converting messages into unreadable figures in order to keep the messages content during the time the message was being transferred from one place to another. In recent times, Cryptography has evolved from message confidentiality to adding some phases of message integrity checking: the authentication of the sender/receiver identity and digital signatures [42]. Cryptography muddles up a secret message such that an unintended recipient finds it difficult to understand. It involves communication which is overt in nature i.e. The existence of communication is detected but not comprehensible to an unintended recipient [55]. The basis of cryptography algorithms is Mathematics.

The Greeks of old used ciphers (algorithms used for encryption and decryption) for cryptography. The cipher functions with the use of a "key" (usually a short string of characters (known

exclusively to the sender and receiver). They used the Caesar Shift Cipher to implement Cryptography by wrapping a tape round a stick, and writing the secret message on the wound tape. When the tape is unwound, the writing becomes meaningless. The recipient then gets a stick of about the same size as that of the sender to read what has been sent [57]. Encryption and decryption in cryptography constitute the two relevant phases [57].

Encryption involves converting a comprehensible text into incomprehensible text called cipher-text [55]. The internet is capable of being kept safe and secure as a result of encryption while decryption is the opposite of encryption. It is converting an incomprehensible text (cipher-text) into a readable one. These two phases are carried out via a cipher which is an algorithm used to carry out the cryptography phases. In cryptography, there are three types of algorithms [57]. The secret key cryptography (SKC) which uses a single key for encryption and decryption.[55]. This is done using symmetric key algorithms such as data encryption standard, DES, advanced encryption standard, AES, MARS, international data encryption algorithm, IDEA, rivet's cipher or ron's Code, RC algorithms such as RC2,RC4,RC5,RC6, Blowfish, two fish, three fish and serpent.

Public key cryptography, PKC uses one key for encryption and another for decryption.[55] PKC uses asymmetric key algorithms such as Diffie-Hellman and Elliptic Curve. Hash functions uses mathematical transformation to encrypt information such that it becomes irreversible.

Steganography

Steganography is a method of hiding information which involves covert communication between a sender and a receiver such that information is hidden within an innocuous cover usually in Text, Image, Audio, Video or Protocol Steganography. The word Steganography comes from the Greek words 'Steganos' and 'Graphia', together mean

"hiding writing"[31].Steganography [73]is the process of secretly embedding information inside a data source without changing its perceptual quality with ultimate intentions are robustness and undetectability [18] . It was further stated that Steganography is the study of techniques for hiding the existence of a secondary message in the presence of a primary message [19]. The primary message is referred to as the carrier signal or carrier message; the secondary message is referred to as the payload signal or payload message. It hides messages inside other harmless carrier in a way that does not allow any enemy to even detect that there is a second message present [10].

It can be said to be the art and science of writing hidden messages in such a way that no one, apart from the sender and intended recipient, suspects the existence of the message, form of security through obscurity [24]. This differs from Cryptography, which make a message unreadable by a third party but does not hide the existence of the secret communication. Although Steganography is separate and distinct from Cryptography; many analogies exist between the two, some authors categorize Steganography as a form of Cryptography since hidden communication is a form of secret writing. Steganography hides one medium of information in another medium [13] [16].

The aim of Steganography[72] is to hide the secret data inside the cover medium without changing the overall quality of cover medium. It involves not just concealing a message but also making the existence of the secret message undetectable [40].

In Steganography, the actual information is not maintained in its original format but is converted in such a way that it can be hidden inside multimedia file. The entertainment industry (Music and Movie) have their arms open to new Steganography techniques. Cybercrimes are also curtailed by different Steganography techniques. Some of the techniques used to implement Steganography include cover generation methods, distortion techniques, statistical method, spread spectrum techniques and transform domain technique. The most common types of

Steganography [36] (based on their cover files) are text Steganography, image steganography, audio Steganography and video steganography commonly referred to as the video forensic.

Text Steganography [33] is a technique of hiding a secret message within a text file. It involves [36] altering an existing text, modifying words in a text, to bringing forth random character sequences or making use of context-free grammars to bring forth readable text. Text Steganography can be done by either altering the format or meaning of a text message.

There are three (3) main categories of Text Steganography[36]. They include format based in which the existing text is modified in order to hide the steganographic text; the random and statistical generation: utilizes [37] word and character sequences to embed data; the linguistic methods which involves the replacement of the original word with another word that possesses almost the same meaning as the original word.

Image steganography [33][74] involves using an image file as the cover object for embedding a secret message. Steganography [39] in images are classified into spatial domain based Steganography in which the secret messages are embedded directly using Least Significant Bit (LSB) and sometimes the blocks technique is used. The second is the transform domain based Steganography. This technique is used to hide a large amount of data. The. image steganography [43] is usually done using the following techniques: least significant bit insertion, masking and filtering, redundant pattern encoding, encrypt and scatter, algorithms and transformations.

Audio Steganography [35] is a method of hiding a data file of lower embedding capacity in an Audio file in order to prevent unintended recipients from gaining access to it .It also is an appropriate Steganography medium due to its high data transmission rate and high level of

redundancy. audio steganography [19] is focused in hiding secret information in an innocent cover Audio file or signal securely and strongly. The secret message is embedded by slightly altering the binary sequence of a sound file. Existing audio steganography software can embed messages in WAV, AU, and even MP3 sound files. An effective Audio Steganography scheme should possess the following three characteristics: inaudibility of distortion (perceptual transparency), data rate (capacity) and robustness. These characteristics are called the magic triangle for data hiding. In this type of Steganography secret messages can be embedded into digital sound in audio steganography. It is more complex process as compare to embedding messages in other media [24][53].[15]There are three basic methods for Steganography as Injection, Substitution and Generation. Audio steganography has various applications like digital watermarking, access control, covert communication, etc. Already there are lots of Audio Steganography techniques which have been used in hiding the data. Such techniques are [43] echo hiding LSB technique, parity coding, spread spectrum.

Video Steganography is also known as [9] Video Forensics.[17][32][33]. It entails information being enveloped inside a Video to make it safe from intruders [3]. Video file is composed of an Audio file and moving [9][30][33]Image files. Table transform domain based techniques are considered to be less prone to attacks due to high security. Digital image is a collection of pixels which are present in high and low frequency components of image. The edge pixels are high frequency pixels and non edge pixels are low frequency pixels. Some techniques of video steganography are [31] include transform domain technique: The secret message is hidden in the change space (recurrence area) of the spread, that is, discrete wavelet transform, DWT, Discrete cosine transform, DCT and discrete sine transform, DST. The second is the spread spectrum technique which adopts the thought of spread reach such that the message is spread over a repeat transmission limit. The third is the statistical technique which function such that the spread is separated into pieces and each piece

is used to cover one message bit . If the message is bit is one , then the spread square is adjusted generally the spread piece is not changed. The forth is the distortion technique in which the encoder applies an arrangement of alterations to the spread. This grouping compares to the mystery message. The fifth is the protection of data alteration in which the delicacy of the inserted information in the application zone is exploited.

The research of Video Steganography techniques can be explored in effective selection of cover media. In order to identify methods for embedding secret message some characteristics are put into consideration. Some of which are: high imperceptibility, high embedding capacity, high embedding efficiency with optimum data hiding locations, low computational cost of data retrieval and data embedding rate, high security, different Video files extension, different types of secret message like Video inside Video, image inside Video, Audio inside Video. Video Steganography has quite number of strengths over other Steganography techniques . Some [21]of which are the capability of Videos outweighs images, video files have the capacity to embed quite a lot of data, covert communication is carried out well and secret data is well kept, data are well protected against alteration, access control system for digital content distribution Media Database system. Phases involved in steganography are embedding in which the stegosystem encoder is used to place a secret message (primary message) within a cover work (secondary message) in order to produce a stegogramme or stego file. The communication phase is a phase in which a secret key (which is known exclusively to the sender and recipient) is generated for use at the Embedding Phase as well as the Extraction Phase. Extraction phase is the phase in which the secret key is used on the stegogramme in order to separate the secret message from the cover work.

Methodology

Description of the Existing System

D.J Bode, Salunkhe Vaishali, ShetePuja, Shinde Govind and Shinde Rupesh [30] developed a system that implemented both Image and Audio Steganography using FZDH algorithm for Image Steganography and Phase Coding for Audio Steganography. Its security feature was enhanced by using histogram matching and Peak Signal Noise Ratio (PSNR) at both the sender and receiver's side.

The system which comprises of two sides: The Sender's Side and the Receiver's Side.

At the sender's end, a Video file is selected. Afterwards, the audio frame and video parts of the Video are separated. The video part is then separated into a number of frames. The frame number is selected from the video file, which is used for hiding the image using FZDH Algorithm to generate a Stego Video file. The secret text message is also hidden within the Audio file using Phase Coding Algorithm to generate a Stego Audio file. The Stego Video and Stego Audio are then fused together to give a StegoVideo file. The Stego Video file is then sent via a communication channel such as the internet from the Sender's Side to the Receiver's Side. At the receiver's end, the StegoVideo is received and the Audio and Video files are extracted from the StegoVideo file. The frame number (pass key) is entered. If the frame number is identical to both sides, then the authentication is carried out, else, abort. After authentication for extracting hidden data from the Video file, the PSNR (Peak Signal Noise Ratio) and Histogram are checked if they are identical or not. If they are identical, then receiver extracts information, else, abort.

Description of the Proposed System

The proposed system is intended to be implemented using a multi-layer approach

involving Cryptography and Steganography. It is functional at two (2) ends: The sender's end and the receiver's end. At the sender's end, it involves selecting a video file and then, demultiplexing (splitting) the Audio file from the Video file and then typing in an encryption key as well as the secret message and then embedding the encrypted message in the audio file to form a Stego Audio. Then the Stego Audio is multiplexed (merged) with the Video (moving images without sound from original video file) to form the StegoVideo. At the receiver's end, the steganoframe (moving image frames) is removed from the StegoVideo and the StegoAudio called "RecAudio" is selected and the secret message is extracted while it is also being decrypted and this gives rise to the secret message. An image file was not embedded within the video part of the file just like in the existing system because it was observed that by so doing, the video file would reduce in quality and clarity.

Software Development Life Cycle

The Waterfall Model was used during the course of software development and the reason is simply because it is relatively simple to implement and it gives the opportunity for one to re-visit the steps until it is completed [43]. The steps involved in the Waterfall Model are analysis which involves carrying out Software Requirements Specification (SRS) such that a complete and comprehensive structure of the system to be developed is created such that the functional and non-functional requirements are clearly spelt out. Design entails putting up building blocks for the design of the software. Implementation requires code writing and compilation into an operational application. Testing which entails checking if the software meets the intended requirements at the beginning of the development. Maintenance entails modifying software after delivery and

deployment to improve the performance[43].

Architecture of the Existing System

Fig 1

Fig 2

Architecture of the Proposed System

Implementation

Java Programming Language as well as C/C++ were used for the development of this project. Java was used in Steganography because of its efficient security features while C/C++ was used in implementing multiplexing and de-multiplexing because it possesses a fast run time.. AES Algorithm was used for cryptography because of the ease of usage of the algorithm. Net-Beans was chosen as an Integrated Development Environment (IDE) because of its user friendly structure.

At the Sender's end, the Video Steganography executable file is launched and opens up a Video Steganography GUI.

Sample Interfaces

Fig 3

This GUI made up a "Select video" label at the top left hand corner of the form, "video file" box to the right of the "Select video" and a "Search" button at the top right hand

corner of the form. It also has the "Video Name" label which states the name of the video selected and "Video type" label which states the type and size of the video file.

Fig 4

At this point, the User selects the audio file which was extracted from the original video file and then clicks on the Refreshes Info button in order to display the details of the audio file.

An encryption key is then entered (User types in any strings of his/her choice) and shouldn't be more than sixteen (16) characters since the AES algorithm used, uses a block cipher of 128 bit. It is strongly advised that the User not only keeps the secret key safe and secure but also simple and concise in order to prevent the User from forgetting it. The secret message is then typed into the "enter message" box and then click on the "Embedding" button.

Afterwards, the secret message would have been embedded in the Audio file in order to generate a Stego-Audio file.

Fig 5

At the receiver's end, then the "RecAudio file" is selected (RecAudio is the Stego-

Audio embedded in the video) and the decryption key is entered (same as sender's encryption key) .

Fig 6

A file name is generated for the text file .We can name it "secret text" and would be saved

in Video folder on the Desktop.

Fig 7

At the end of it all, the secret message is extracted for use by the receiver as seen in the GUI on the previous page.

Testing

The software would pass through different phases of testing in order to know if it meets up the required

specifications. [44]Testing is the process of executing a program with the intent of finding errors.

Table 1: UNIT TEST CASES ON DEMULTIPLEXING

TEST CASE ID	TESTCASE DESC.	PRECOND.	TEST INPUT	EXP. RESULT	ACT. RESULT	STATUS
1	Demux	None	Video File	Separated audio and Video	Audio and Video files	Valid
2	Demux	None	Audio File	Separated audio and Video	Invalid	Invalid
3	Demux	None	Image	Separated Audio and Video	Invalid	Invalid
4	Demux	None	Text	Separated audio and Video	Invalid	Invalid

The unit test case on de-multiplexing simply shows that the de-multiplexing function of the software (as seen in the

table) can only de-multiplex a video file, while it will not work on an audio, image and text files as the system would not generate any valid output.

Table 2: UNIT TEST CASE ON EMBEDDING

TEST CASE ID	TESTCASE DESC.	PRECOND	TEST INPUT	EXP. RESULT	ACT. RESULT	STATUS
1	Embed	Separated Audio and Text	Text and Audio	StegoAudio	Stego Audio	Valid
2	Embed	Separated Audio and Text	Audio and Audio	StegoAudio	Invalid	Invalid
3	Embed	Separated Audio and Text	Video and Text	StegoAudio	Invalid	Invalid
4	Embed	Separated Audio and Text	Text and	StegoAudio	Invalid	Invalid

The first case of unit testing under the embedding function of the software is used to infuse encrypted text within the audio in order to generate a StegoAudio. Though, there is a precondition which requires that there should be a separated audio and text file prior the embedding. The second test, involves embedding an audio within another audio file, which does not yield any valid output. The third test involves embedding a video within a text which is virtually impossible because a video file has a higher embedding capacity than a text file. The fourth test involves embedding a text within a text which will not yield any result because the software will not be able to execute this, since it wasn't built for it.

Table 3: UNIT TEST CASE ON MULTIPLEXING

TEST CASE ID	TESTCASE DESC.	PRECOND	TEST INPUT	EXP. RESULT	ACT. RESULT	STATUS
1	Mux	Stego Audio and Video	Stego Audio and Video	Stego Video	Stego Video	Valid
2	Mux	Stego Audio and Video	Audio and Audio	Stego Video	Invalid	Invalid
3	Mux	Stego Audio and Video	Video and Text	Stego Video	Invalid	Invalid
4	Mux	Stego Audio and Video	Text and Text	Stego Video	Invalid	Invalid

The multiplexing test case helps to check if the system carries out the multiplexing function as expected. It needs a precondition of a Stego Audio and Video files to be available before the multiplexing can be done. The first test case has the Stego Audio and

Video as input and the expected result is a Stego Video. While the second test has two audio files as input and this generates an invalid output. The third and fourth tests have Video and text as well as two text files as input. They also generate invalid results.

Table 4: UNIT TEST CASES ON EXTRACTING

TEST CASE ID	TESTCASE DESC.	PRECOND.	TEST INPUT	EXP. RESULT	ACT. RESULT	STATUS
1	Extract	StegoAudio File	StegoAudio File	Audio and Text files	Audio and Text files	Valid
2	Extract	StegoAudio File	StegoVideo File	Audio and Text files	Invalid	Invalid
3	Extract	StegoAudio File	Image	Audio and Text files	Invalid	Invalid
4	Extract	StegoAudio File	Text	Audio and Text files	Invalid	Invalid

The extract function needs to have an already created Stego Audio file in place. During the first test, the Stego Audio file is then acted upon by the extract function which then generates the Audio and Text files. The second test involves a Stego Video file , which would not produce the expected result. The third and fourth tests involve having both image and

text as input files, which would never generate audio and text files as output.

Summary

This entire research work centers on securing information from being accessed by unauthorized personnel; as this may cause loss of vital information or sabotage which could cost an individual, institution or even a nation to run at a loss. In order to prevent this from happening, this research was developed to keep text files safe and secure while using a video file as a cover to camouflage the existence of the text file while also implementing cryptography such that peradventure, a hacker attempt accessing the text, it would be incomprehensible.

Conclusion

In conclusion, from the implementation of this research, it can be seen vividly that Cryptography and Steganography are very powerful information hiding tools which help prevent hackers from gaining access to important information. This work clearly shows that the LSB algorithm has high embedding capacity and the AES algorithm is relatively fast when compared with other symmetric cryptographic algorithms.

Recommendations

For the purpose of future research, other researchers may need to explore other areas of Steganography such as Network/Protocol Steganography which is not very common today. As well as also delve into other Cryptography algorithms, particularly asymmetric key cryptography for the implementation of Cryptography. More security can be added to the current system by incorporating the input of username and password as log in credentials.

References

- [1] S. Singhania, S. Gupta, B. Bhushan and A. Nain. " A Novel Crypt - StegoTechnique for Information Security in Communication Networks", *International Journal of Signal Processing, Image Processing and Pattern Recognition*, Vol. 6, No. 2, April, 2013
- [2] D. Singla and R. Syal. " Data Security Using LSB & DCT Steganography InImages ",*International Journal Of Computational Engineering Research/ ISSN: 2250–3005 IJ CER | Mar-Apr 2012 | Vol. 2 | Issue No.2 |359-364 Page 359*
- [3] R. Kaur and D. Aggarwal. " Analysis of Secure Text Embedding using Steganography", *International Journal of Latest Trends in Engineering and Technology (IJLTET)* Vol. 2 Issue 1 January 2013
- [4] A.Halder ,S.Roy, I. Das and S. Panda. " An Amalgamation of Steganographyand Cryptography ", *International Journal of Latest Trends in Engineering and Technology (IJLTET)* Vol. 3 Issue 4 March 2014
- [5] A. K Singh, J. Singh and H. V. Singh."Steganography in Images Using LSB Technique" *International Journal of Latest Trends in Engineering and Technology (IJLTET)* Vol. 5 Issue 1 January 2015
- [6] A. Sharma and A. Mohammed " Three Level Wavelet Decomposition Hybrid Transform Image Steganography"*International Journal Of Advanced Electronics & Communication Systems* Issue 2 VOL 3, April-May-2014
- [7]S. Dhall, B. Bhushan and S. Gupta "An In-depth Analysis of Various Steganography Techniques" *International Journal of Security and Its Applications* Vol.9.No.8(2015),pp.67-94

<http://dx.doi.org/10.14257/ijasia.2015.9.8.07>

[8] P. T. Anitha, M. Rajaram and S. N. Sivanandham, "Analysis of Detecting Steganography contents in corporate Emails" *International Journal of Research and Reviews in Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJRRECE)* Vol. 1, No. 2, June 2011.

[9] Dr. A.K.Sen, S. Dutta and S. Dabadgaonkar "Echo Hiding Approach in Video Forensic" *International Journal Of Innovative Research In Electrical, Electronics, Instrumentation And Control Engineering (IJREEICE)* Vol. 1, Issue 1, April 2013.

[10] V. Nagaraj, Dr. V. Vijayalakshmi, and Dr. G. Zayaraz "Overview of Digital Steganography Methods and Its Applications" *International Journal of Advanced Science and*

[11] Y. Lee "Streaming Video Service Model using Secure Steganographic Method" *International Journal of Security and Its Applications* Vol.7, No.6 (2013), pp.79-88

[12] M. P. Singh and H. Singh "An Efficient Modified LSB technique for Video Steganography" *International Journal of Advanced Research in Electrical, Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering (IJAREEIE)* Vol. 4, Issue 6, June 2015.

[13] Ms. V. Sarangpure, Mrs. R. B. Talmale and Ms. M. Domke "Survey paper-Audio-Video Steganography Using Anti Forensics Technique" *International Journal of Research (IJR)* Vol-1, Issue-9, October 2014 ISSN 2348-6848

[14] S. Pal and Prof. S. Kr Bandyopadhyay "Various Methods Of Video Steganography" *International Journal of Information Research and Review (IJIRR)* Vol.03, Issue 06, pp.2569-2573, June, 2016.

[15] P. Rameshkumar, M. Monisha and B. Santhi "Enhancement of Information Hiding in Audio Signals with Efficient LSB based Methods" *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, Vol. 7(S4), 80-85, April 2014.

[16] Praveen. P and Arun. R "Audio-Video Crypto Steganography using LSB Substitution and Advanced Chaotic Algorithm" *International Journal of Engineering Inventions* e-ISSN: 2278-7461, p-ISSN: 2319-6491 Volume 4, Issue 2 (August 2014) PP: 01-07 www.ijejournal.com Page | 1.

B. Chandel and Dr. S Jain "Video Steganography: A Survey" *IOSR Journal of Computer Engineering (IOSR-JCE)* e-ISSN: 2278-0661, p-ISSN: 2278-8727, Volume 18, Issue 1, Ver. III (Jan – Feb. 2016), PP 11-17 www.iosrjournals.org DOI: 10.9790/0661-18131117 www.iosrjournals.org 11 | Page *Technology* Vol.60, (2013), 58. <http://dx.doi.org/10.142>

[17] A. Swathi and Dr. S.A.K Jilani, Ph.D "Video Steganography by LSB Substitution Using Different Polynomial Equations" *International Journal Of Computational Engineering Research (ijceronline.com)* Vol. 2 Issue. 5, Sep. 2012

[19] V. Yadav, S. Gupta and V. Jaiswal "Implementation of Audio Steganography Using C#" *International Journal of Technology Management & Humanities (IJTMH)* e-ISSN: 2454 – 566X, Volume 1, Issue 2, (September 2015)

[20] R. Doshi, P. Jain and L. Gupta "Steganography and Its Applications in Security" *International Journal of Modern Engineering Research (IJMER)* www.ijmer.com Vol.2, Issue.6, Nov-Dec. 2012 pp-4634-4638 ISSN: 2249-6645 www.ijmer.com 4634 |

[21] Dr. N. Agrawal and Ms. P. Mor "Empirical

Study of Algorithms and Techniques of Video Steganography" *Journal for Research/ Volume 01/ Issue 12 /February 2016 ISSN: 2395-7549*

[22] Dr. S. Bhattacharyya, I. Banerjee and Prof (Dr.)G. Sanyal" A Survey of Steganography and Steganalysis Technique in Image, Text, Audio and Video as Cover Carrier"*Journal of Global Research in Computer Science Volume 2, No. 4, April 2011, www.jgrcs.info*

[23]N. Kau and S. Behal, "Audio Steganography Techniques-A Survey " *Int. Journal of Engineering Resear and Applications www.ijera.com ISSN : 2248-9622, Vol. 4, Issue 6(Ver 5), June 2014, pp.94-100*

[25]D. Lalwani, M. Sawant, M. Rane, V.Jogdande and S.B.Ware "Secure Data Hiding inAudio-VideoSteganalysis byAnti-Forensic Technique" *International Journal Of Engineering And Computer Science ISSN:2319-7242Volume -5 Issue - 3 March, 2016 Page No.15996-16000*

[26] T. Sruthi and D. Srihari, "An Interlaced Approach of Audio Steganography and Cryptography Using LSB Algorithms with Logical Operators " *International Journal of Engin eering Research- Online"Vol.3., Issue.5.,2015 (Sept-Oct.) http://www.ijoer.in*

[27] P. N. Phartade and Prof. V.Navale, " Component of Data Hiding In Audio-Video Using Anti Forensics Technique for Data Authentication " *International Journal of*

Innovative Research in Computer and Engineering Vol.4 ,Issue 6, June 2016.

[27] P. S. Babu and Dr. M. Prabu," Visteal-Videos Transmission and Encryption within an Auxiliary Video " *International Journal of Advanced Research (2016), Volume 4 , Issue 7, 1256-1260*

[28] K.P. Adhiya and Swati A. Patil "Hiding Text in Audio Using LSB Based Steganography" *Information and Knowledge Management , ISSN 2224- 5758(Paper) ISSN 2224-896X(Online) Vol. 2 No. 3, 2012 www.ijste.com*

[29] D.JBonde, S.Govind, S.Vaishali, S. Puja, S.Rupesh "Application of Data Hiding Using Anti-Forensic Technique" *International Journal of Engineering Science and Computing, March,2016.*

[31]Er. Ginni, Er. Pushpinder Singh "A Review on Secure Video Steganography Technique using LSB & MSB" *International Journal of Advance Research in Computer and Communication Engineering Vol. 5. Issue 3, March,2016.*

[32]S. Choubey, G.Shrivastava " A Novel Method of Video Steganography Using Variable LSB" *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering Vol. 5, Issue 7, July,2015.*

[33]A. Patel and A. Barot "A Survey Paper on Video Steganography" *International Journal for Scientific Research and Development Vol.3, Issue 12,2016 / ISSN (online): 2321-0613*

[34]Y. Kakde, P. Gonnade and P. Dahiwalde " Audio Video Steganography for Authentication and Data Security" *Journal of Emerging Technologies and InnovativeResearch(JETIR),www.jetir.org, June*

2015, Volume 2, Issue 6.

[35] A. Z. Al-Othman, A. A Manaf and A. M. Zeki "A Survey on Steganography Techniques in Real Time Audio Signals and Evaluation" *International Journal of Computer Science Issues (IJCSI)* www.IJCSI.org, Vol. 9, Issue 1, No.1, January 2012

[36] A. Koluguri, S. Gouse and Dr. P. Bhaskara Reddy "Text Steganography Methods and its Tools" *International Journal of Advanced Scientific and Technical Research* Issue 4 volume 2, March-April 2014 ISSN 2249-9954

[37] R. Amirtharajan and J. B. BalaguruRayappan "Steganography -Time to Time: A Review" *Research Journal of Information Technology*, February 2013

[38] S. Istapute, S. Shahane and S. Singh, "An Approach Towards Video Steganography Using FZDH(Forbidden Zone Data Hiding)" *International Journal of Innovations and Advancement in Computer Science IJIACS* ISSN 2347- 8616, Volume 4, Issue 1, January, 2015.

[39] Mr. Falesh M. Shelke, Miss Ashwini A. Dongre and Mr. Pravin D. Soni "Comparison of Different Techniques for Steganography in Images" *International Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering and Management (IJAIEM)* www.ijaiem.com, Vol. 3, Issue 2, February, 2014.

[40] B. Padmasri and M. AmuthaSurabi "Spread Spectrum Image Steganography with Advanced Encryption Key Implementation" *International Journal of Advanced Research in*

Computer Science and Software Engineering www.ijarcsse.com, Vol. 3 Issue 3, March, 2013.

[41] N. Meghanathan and L. Nayak "Steganalysis Algorithms for Detecting the Hidden Information in Image and Audio and Video Cover Media" *International Journal of Network Security and Its Applications (IJNSA)*, Vol. 2, No. 1, January, 2010

[35] Abhishek, G. Jagnade, L. Madhuri, P. Mehta and R. Seth "Data Security Using Cryptosteganography in Web Application" *Computer Engineering and Intelligent Systems*, Vol. 3, No. 4, 2012, www.iiste.org.

[36] Y. Bassil, "Simulation Model for the Waterfall Software Development Life Cycle" *International Journal of Engineering & Technology (iJET)*, ISSN: 2049-3444, Vol. 2, No. 5, 2012.

[37] K.K. Aggarwal and Y. Singh, *Software Engineering* (3rd Edition)

[38] Pramatha Nath Basu, "On Embedding of Text in Audio - A case of Steganography" *International Conference on Recent Trends in Information, Telecommunication and Computing*, 2010.

[39] www.staff.um.edu.mt/csta1/seminars/interne_t_seminar.html

[40] The Future of Children " *Children And Computer Technology*" Vol. 10. No. 2 _Fall/Winter 2000

[41] *International Journal of Cognitive Research in Science, Engineering and Education (IJCRSEE)* Vol. 1, No. 2, 2013. www.ijcrsee.com/index.php/ijcrsee/article/view/63/180

- [42] www.livestrong.com/article/125838-benefits-children-using-computers/
- [43] www.smallbusiness.chron.com/adventages-using-internet-business-320.html
- [44] J. Kour and D.Verma,"Steganography Techniques-A Review Paper"*International Journal of Emerging Research in Management and Technology. ISSN:2278-9359 (Volume- 3, Issue -5). May,201*
- [52]F.Djebbar,B. Ayad,Karim Abed Meraim andHabib Hamam,"Comparative Study of Digital Audio Steganography Techniques"*EURASIP Journal on Audio,Speech and Music Processing ,December,2012.*
- [53] Jayaram,Ranganatha H.R and Anupama H.S,"Information Hiding Using Audio Steganography - A Survey", *The International Journal of Multimedia and Its Applications (IJMA) Vol.3, No.3, August 2011.*
- [54] https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=H_N5_vxs8Tg
- [55] www.globalsign.com/en/blog/glossary-of-cryptographic-algorithms/
- [56]S Hasan Al-Bakri, M.L Mat Kiah, A.A Zaidan, B.B Zaidan and Gazi Mahabubul Alam, "Securing Peer-To-Peer Mobile Communications Using Public Key Cryptography: New Security Strategy", *International Journal of Physical Science, 2011.*
- [57] Prof. Waghmare, Simran Sikhwal, Shreyas Nimje and Tanvi Pawar, "History of Cryptography", *International Journal for Technological Research in Engineering,Vol.4, Issue 8, April 2017.*
- [58] J Thakur and N Kumar," DES,AES and Blowfish: Symmetric Key Cryptography Algorithms Simulation Based Performance Analysis", *International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering, Vol. 1 Issue 2, December, 2011.*
- [59] Debiao He, Muhammad Khurram Khan and Shuhua Wu, " On The Security of an RSA-Based Certificateless Signature Scheme", *International Journal of Network Security , Vol. 16, No.1, PP. 78- 80, Jan.2014.*
- [60] Federal Information Processing Standards Publication{Book}, Nov.2001
- [61] Joni Monttinen, " The Security of Advanced Encryption Standard", 2015.
- [62] R. Ravi Kumar and V. Kesav Kumar, "Selective Embedding and Forbidden Zone Data Hiding for Strong Video Data Thashing", *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology(IJETT), Vol. 4 Issue 9-Sep.2013*
- [63] Kelsey Rauber, "Cloud Cryptography", *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics , Vol. 85 No. 1 2013, 1-11*
- [64] M. S Atoum, G. Sulong and A. Zeki "Exploring the Challenges of MP3 Audio Steganography"www.researchgate.net/publication/269300336
- [65] M. Tayel and H. Shawky, " A Proposed Assessment Metrics for Image Steganography" *International Journal on Cryptography and InformationSecurity(IJCIS), Vol.4, No.1, March,2014.*
- [66] Mr. B. Bharathi, Mr. G. Manivasagam and Dr.M. Anand Kumar,

"Metrics for Performance Evaluation of Encryption Algorithms" *International Journal of Advance Research in Science and Engineering*, Vol.No.6, Issue No.03, March 2017. www.ijarse.com

[67] N. D. Jorstad, "Cryptographic Algorithm Metrics " *Institute for Defense Analyses Science and Technology*, January 1997.

[68] H. Goyal and P. Bansal " An Analytical Study on Video Steganography" *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science*", Vol. 6, No. 5, May-June, 2015.

[69] www.researchgate.net/post/How_to_measure_throughput_of_AES_algorithm

[70] G. Singh and Supriya, "A Study of Encryption Algorithms (RSA, and DES) for Information Security" *International Journal of Computer Applications*, Vol.67- No. 19, April 2013.

[71] Vijay Kumar, Saloni Laddha, Aniket Sharma, Nitin Dogra "Steganography Techniques Using Convolutional Neural Networks" <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/3443792812020> (2020)

[72] Daniya Sakina S. Murugavalli S B, Jabasheela L C,*, Anitha V "Ceaseless steganographic approaches in machine learning" ELSEVIER(2022) www.sciencedirect.com/journal/measurement-sensors

[73] R. Gurunath1, Ahmed H. Alahmadi 2, Debabrata Samanta 1, (member, iee),

Mohammad Zubair Khan 2, and Abdulrahman Alahmadi "Novel Approach For Linguistic Steganography Evaluation Based On Artificial Neural Networks" (2021)

[74] Arivazhagan Selvaraj Amrutha Ezhilarasan Sylvia Lilly Jebarani Wellington Ananthi Roy Sam "Digital image steganalysis: A survey on paradigm shift from machine learning to deep learning based techniques" DOI: 10.1049/ipr2.12043 *IET Image Processing* published by John Wiley & Sons Ltd on behalf of The Institution of Engineering and Technology (2020)

[75] K.P. Adhiya and Swati A. Patil "Hiding Text in Audio Using LSB Based Steganography" *Information and Knowledge Management*, ISSN 2224-5758 (Paper) ISSN 2224-896X (Online) Vol. 2 No. 3, www.ijste.com 2012

[76] Dr. A.K.Sen, S. Dutta and S. Dabadgaonkar "Echo Hiding Approach in Video Forensic" *International Journal Of Innovative Research In Electrical, Electronics, Instrumentation And Control Engineering (IJIREICE)* Vol. 1, Issue 1, April 2013.

[77] N. Kau and S. Behal, "Audio Steganography Techniques-A Survey " *Int. Journal of Engineering Research and Applications* www.ijera.com ISSN : 2248-9622, Vol. 4, Issue 6 (Version 5), June 2014, pp.94-100